

SORSE Workshops: FAIR4RS

17 November 2020

Session 1 Breakout Room 3 Notes

Title: How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR?

Lead: Paula Andrea Martinez
Participants: everyone

Open question, please add your thoughts.

Fotis: **Citation** and **formal** Institutional **recognition** of such citations towards professional development.

Matthias: (disclaimer: I don't write research software). Treat software as a first-class research output. Make the **incentives for writing "good" software** the same as performing "good" research. Make the disincentives the same.

Axel: being able to **factor** in resources in **grants**

Cunliang: to be **cited in publications**, to get users' feedback and usage statistics

Teri: GitHub (or other) **label/badge** to say it is FAIR. Publication of software in a particular journal/article where software is assessed to see if it is FAIR. All collaborators (including non-coders) get **credit** in github/papers. Better metrics on who is using the software (both as is, as part of a larger system, or "inspired by").

Carlos: Best **recognition** for my software would be if people would use it (but then I would like to be able to track how many people are using it).

Morane: with a **FAIR badge**, like with the ACM badges, giving a "better" notion to the software

Stephan Janosch: Help the **recognition** as RSE. Providing indication, that RSEs need to be available as central facility.

Markus: Software should be on the **same level as a paper**, given that it is new, original, reviewed etc.

Anna-Lena: technically, maybe a “**FAIR badge**” for repositories and software, but also organizations need to **reward** such efforts in **hiring/tenure/promotion procedures**

Malin: I had an interesting discussion on Twitter about authorship, responsibility, and credit : Thread starts here <https://twitter.com/AnneEUrai/status/1327934091929464832>
TL/DR we need a wider scope of credit/author roles including overall responsibility without doing anything but review/approve work

Malin: also, code contributor roles are a lot more complex than article author roles.

Malin: I recommend a look at how the BIDS community assigns credit:
<https://bids-specification.readthedocs.io/en/latest/99-appendices/01-contributors.html>

Resources:

- <http://credit.niso.org/>
- A Tale of Software Citation Pitfalls, van de Sandt, Stephanie; Ioannidis, Alex
<https://zenodo.org/record/4263762#.X7OVkq4RXs0> November 9, 2020 Poster Open Access
- Software Citation Checklist for Authors, Chue Hong, Neil et al.
<https://zenodo.org/record/3479199#.X7OVbK4RXs0> October 15, 2019
- ACM badges: <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-badging>
- Badge for compliance with <https://fair-software.eu/> recommendations:
<https://github.com/fair-software/howfairis>

Transcribed comments:

<label/badge>:

- Carlos Martinez: Shameless advertising: <https://github.com/fair-software/howfairis>